

“Na baro kè” Subtitle Conventions

Updated: 2019-06-12

Manding-Latin Transcript Line

Symbols

CONVENTION	DESCRIPTION	REPRESENTATION
(word)	Parentheses	Transcriber’s best interpretation of unclear or unintelligible speech into standard orthography;
{word ¹ }	Curly brackets	A marked orthographic representation when pronunciation is clearly distinct from conventional orthography
[implicit words ²]	Square brackets	Implied word or information; Word added for clarity
...	Three periods	Clear pause; Ellipsis
(...)	Three periods between parentheses	Unclear or unintelligible speech
clipped-	Hyphen at end of a word	Halting or abrupt cut off of sound or word
turn - taking	Space-hyphen-space	Participant turn-taking in a single subtitle
"reported"	Quotation marks	Reported speech; Metalinguistic discussion

Conventions for interjections, verbal tickets, speech gestures etc.

CONVENTION	BAMADABA FORMS	ENGLISH	DESCRIPTION
Anhaan	Ànháàn	Alright!	Interjection that signals something like “Alright, I’ve understood or got it”
ɛ	É	Ah!	Interjection marking a cheerful surprise or admiration
ɛɛ	Éɛ	Ah!	Interjection marking shock or incredulity
Èhɛ	Èhé	Hey!	Interjection used to call someone’s attention
Haan	Hàan; haa		Interjection to express surprise during story-telling or preaching that can be glossed “Pas possible!” in French or “Whoa; wow; holy smokes!”
Hiya	híye		Interjection of incredulity. Often used in one’s own story. Equivalent to “ça alors!” or “ah ça” in French.
Onhon	ònhón	Yes, yeah	
On-hon	ón-òñ	No	
Mm	Mm, hm, hùn		Humming-sound (often marking of agreement or attention to one’s interlocutor)

¹ This convention has been added and is formally applied to ELAN project files starting with Episode 3.

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On			Filler discourse particle or an interjection similar to ‘alright’, ‘well’ or ‘yeah’
Yε	Yé		Exclamation of surprise or admiration

For loanwords or nonce borrowings that are not significantly phonologically assimilated into Manding such as *mais*, *direction* etc., I preserve their French orthography.

For readability’s sake I occasionally omit extraneous repetitions or stuttering.

Tone is generally not marked, except for *à* (3SG) and *á* (2PL). In other cases, I follow the conventions of Bamadaba (Bailleul et al., 2018).

Hyphens appear word internally to mark duplication, “fused” words (Fr. *conglomérés*), and occasionally different constituent elements of tonally compact compound words.

For spelling and word boundaries, I generally follow the proposals of Vydrin & Konta (2014).

English/French Translation Lines

My translations are “free translation;” nonetheless, I aim for more literal translations in English and French when possible

Symbols

CONVENTION	DESCRIPTION	REPRESENTATION
(word)		Implicit word added to the translation
turn - taking	Space-hyphen-space	Participant turn-taking in a single subtitle
clipped-	Hyphen at end of a word	Clipped speech; Halting, abrupt cut off of sound or word.
[additional]	Square brackets	Additional information or a comment from the transcriber
(...)		Unclear or unintelligible speech
"reported"		Reported speech; metalinguistic discussion; Untranslated Manding word

Shortening Conventions

To enable each tier of a subtitle image to fit onto a single line, I often use:

In English, expressions such as *gonna*, *gotta*, etc.

In French, I use *tu* ‘you’ by default regardless of interlocutor and I often do not write out *ne* of the negative marker *ne...pas*.

General

For reasons of space, I sometimes omit non-essential elements that I would normally have preferred for a free translation.

References

- Vydrin, Valentin, and Mahamadou Konta. 2014. "Propositions pour l'orthographe du bamanankan." *Mandenkan* (52): 22–54.
http://llacan.vjf.cnrs.fr/PDF/Mandenkan52/52konta_vydrin.pdf
- Bailleul, Charles, Artem Davydov, Anna Erman, Kirill Maslinsky, Jean Jacques Méric, and Valentin Vydrin. "Bamadaba : Dictionnaire électronique bambara-français, avec un Index français-bambara" (version 2018-06-12). <http://cormand.huma-num.fr/bamadaba.html>.